

Khinis 133 SU1 — Anthropogenic deposit, corral/pastoral use

A-A') General appearance of the microstructure and voids.

B-B') General appearance of the microstructure and voids.

C-C') General appearance of the microstructure and voids. A CaCO_3 clast (white arrow) and a small charcoal fleck (red arrow) are visible.

D-D') Detail of a small bone fragments (white arrows) within a ped.

Khinis 133 SU2

Khinis 133 SU2 — Anthropogenic deposit, corrall/pastoral use

A-A') General appearance of the microstructure and voids of a faecal mass.

B-B') Detail of the fibrous appearance of herbivore faecal mass.

C-C') Detail of faecal spherulites.

D-D') A calcite clast (white arrow) within desiccated silty clay groundmass.

E-E') Bioturbative channels with Fe/Mn oxide quasi-coating (red arrows), shell fragment (white arrow), faecal mass welded to the silty clay groundmass (yellow arrow).

F-F') Interspersed faecal mass fragments and silty clay groundmass, with large structural voids.

G-G') Detail of faecal mass with spherulites.

H-H') Altered faecal pellet (yellow arrow), bioturbative channel with Fe/Mn oxide quasi-coating (red arrow).

I-I') Interspersed faecal mass fragments and silty clay groundmass, with large structural and bioturbative voids. Bone fragment (white arrow).

Khinis 133 SU3

Khinis 133 SU3 — Anthropic deposit, corral/pastoral use

A-A') Interspersed and welded faecal mass fragments and silty clay groundmass, with large structural and bioturbative voids.

B-B') Detail of the fibrous appearance of herbivore faecal mass.

C-C') Detail of faecal spherulites.

D-D') Interspersed and welded faecal mass fragments and silty clay groundmass, with large and bioturbative voids backfilled with debris, and an altered, probably burnt, faecal pellet.

E-E') Detail of the faecal pellet in D-D'.

F-F') Juxtaposed unweled faecal mass and silty clay groundmass, with bioturbative channels.

G-G') Interspersed faecal mass and silty clay groundmass, with large structural voids and large bioturbative channels backfilled with debris. Shell fragment (white arrow).

Khinis 133 SU4

Khinis 133 SU4 — Natural deposit, colluvium

A-A') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with large bioturbative channels and pervasive angular planar voids. Large limestone conglomerate clast on the right hand side.

B-B') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive angular planar voids and amorphous vughs.

C-C') Layered groundmasses differing slightly in colour. Elongated structural voids highlight the discontinuity.

D-D') Darker silty clay groundmass with pervasive presence of vughs.

E-E') Mixed and welded lighter and darker groundmasses, with large structural voids, bioturbative chambers and pervasive thin planar voids.

Khinis 133 SU6 — Natural deposit, colluvium

A-A') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive angular planar voids. Oxide pan nodule (yellow arrow)

B-B') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive angular planar voids. Bone fragment (white arrow)

C-C') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive angular planar voids and large chambers. Radiolarian flint flake (red arrow), limestone clasts in the top right corner.

Khinis 133 SU9 — Natural deposit, colluvium with hydromorphism

A-A') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive subangular planar voids and abundant small vughs and vesicles. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles).

B-B') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive subangular planar voids and abundant small vughs and vesicles. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles).

C-C') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive subangular planar voids and abundant small vughs and vesicles. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles). Micritic calcite within planar voids (white arrow). Calcite impregnation grown within a bioturbative channel (yellow arrow)

D-D') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with pervasive subangular planar voids and abundant small vughs and vesicles. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles). Micritic calcite within planar voids (white arrow). Humus pan impregnation of the silty clay groundmass (yellow circle).

Khinis 133 SU13 — Natural deposit, pedogenized waterlain sediment

A-A') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with bioturbation and pervasive thin planar voids. Preserved plant root tissue (red arrow).

B-B', C-C') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with bioturbation and pervasive thin planar voids. Altered faecal pellets (small mammals, possibly rodent) in the centre of the pictures.

D-D') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with bioturbation and pervasive thin planar voids. Shell fragment (white arrow). Planar voids are organized subhorizontally and suggest layered sedimentation.

E-E') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with bioturbation and pervasive thin planar voids. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles).

F-F', G-G') Desiccated silty clay groundmass with bioturbation and pervasive thin planar voids. Widespread small oxide nodules (dark speckles). Widespread inherited clay microaggregates (orange speckles).

Khinis 834 SU5

Khinis 834 SU5 — Natural deposit, colluvium

A-A') General appearance of the chaotic mixture of silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Pervasive planar voids and bioturbation.

B-B', C-C') Same as A-A'. Shell fragments (white arrows). Pedorelict (yellow arrow).

D-D') Bioturbative canals affect the silty clay groundmass and oxide pans. Fibrous micritic calcite growth within the channels (red arrow).

E-E', F-F') Details of D-D'.

G-G', H-H') Analogous to D-D'.

I-I', J-J') Subhorizontal fine sand pockets within the dessicated silty clay groundmass, with pervasive thin planar voids and abundant vughs and bioturbative channels.

Khinis 834 SU6(1)

Khinis 834 SU6(1) — Natural deposit, colluvium

A-A', B-B') General appearance of the chaotic texture of the silty clay groundmass, with pervasive thin planar voids and abundant vughs and bioturbative channels. Shell fragment (red arrow).

C-C') Large, very altered limestone clast.

Khinis 834 SU6(2) — Natural deposit, colluvium, hydromorphism

A-A', B-B', C-C') General appearance of the chaotic texture of the silty clay groundmass, with pervasive thin planar voids and abundant vughs and bioturbative channels. Colluvial inherited fragments of darker groundmass (yellow arrows). Fibrous micritic calcite growth within the channels (white arrows). Shell fragment (red arrow).

D-D') Patch of dense groundmass with pervasive thin planar voids and abundant small vughs and vesicles.

E-E') Fibrous micritic calcite growth within bioturbative channels.

F-F', G-G') Details of E-E'.

H-H') General appearance of the chaotic mixture of silty clay groundmass and mineral inclusions. Pervasive planar and structural voids.

Khinis 834 SU8

Khinis 834 SU8 — Natural deposit, pedogenized waterlain sediment, hydromorphism

A-A') General appearance of the chaotic mixture of silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Bone fragment (yellow arrow), shell fragments (white arrows). Pervasive bioturbation, vughs and planar voids.

B-B') Silty clay groundmass with pervasive planar voids and small vughs. Evidence of hydromorphism (rusty-coloured patches, red arrow).

C-C') Detail of B-B'.

D-D') Similar to B-B'.

E-E') Similar to B-B'.

F-F') General appearance. Fibrous micritic calcite growing into a bioturbation chamber (white arrow).

G-G') General appearance. Radiolarian chert fragment (yellow arrow).

H-H') General appearance. Residual plant root tissue (yellow arrow).

I-I') General appearance. Fibrous micritic calcite growing into a bioturbation channel (white arrow).

Jerwan 900 SU2

Jerwan 900 SU2 — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvium

A-A' - D-D') General appearance of the groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Shell fragments (white arrow). Pervasive large and incipient angular planar voids bioturbation, common bioturbation and vughs.

E-E') Similar to A-D. Infilling in passage (bioturbation) visible in xpl (yellow arrow).

F-F') Similar to A-D. Humus pan (red arrow).

Jerwan 900 SU4

Jerwan 900 SU4 — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvium

A-A', B-B', C-C') General appearance of the groundmass, with large globular calcite nodules. Pervasive large and incipient planar voids, common bioturbation and small vughs.

D-D', E-E', F-F') General appearance of the groundmass, with pervasive thin and incipient angular planar voids and common bioturbation and small vughs. Shell fragment in D (white arrow).

Jerwan 900 SU7 — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvium

A-A' - D-D') General appearance of the silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Large globular calcite nodule in A. Shell fragment in B (white arrow). Residual plant root tissue inside bioturbation channel in C (yellow arrow) Bone fragment (yellow arrow), shell fragments (white arrows). Pervasive chaotic angular large and incipient planar voids, common small vughs, vesicles and bioturbation.

Jerwan 900 SU9bottom

Jerwan 900 SU9bottom

Jerwan 900 SU9bottom

Jerwan 900 SU9bottom — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvial/waterlain sediment, hydromorphism

A-A' - G-G') General appearance of the silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Bone fragments (white arrows), worm biomineralizations (yellow arrows), evidence of hydromorphism (rusty-coloured patches, red arrow), residual plant root tissue (green arrow). Pervasive subangular planar voids, common vughs, vesicles and structural voids.

H-H') General appearance of the silty clay hydromorphic groundmass, with unidentified possible shell fragments (white arrow).

I-I') Detail of H. The fragments are extremely thin — they might be heavily pedogenized, or have a different origin altogether.

Jerwan 900 SU9 — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvial/waterlain sediment, hydromorphism

A-A' - D-D') General appearance of chaotic silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Pervasive angular and subangular planar voids, common small vughs and vesicles. Large amorphous calcite nodule in D.

Jerwan 900 SU9top — Natural deposit, pedogenized colluvium

A-A', B-B', C-C') General appearance of chaotic silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Large amorphous calcite nodules growing within the dense network of thin angular and subangular planar voids.

D-D' - H-H') General appearance of chaotic silty clay groundmass and mineral/organic inclusions. Dense network of large and incipient angular and subangular planar voids, sometimes transitioning to structural voids. Common vughs and vesicles also present.